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SEQUENCE ANALYSIS OF MTND2 GENE IN FAMILIES SEGREGATING MATERNALLY INHERITED CVDS FROM DISTRICT MANSEHRA

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ABSTRACT

Mitochondria, which are the cellular powerhouses, produce approximately 95% of the adenosine triphosphate (ATP) molecules required through cellular respiration. The aim of this study was to investigate mutations in mitochondrial encoded NADH dehydrogenase subunit 2 (mtND2) in CVD patients from District Mansehra, Pakistan. Blood specimens were collected from a total of 16 people from 5 distinct families, and DNA was extracted from these samples. Subsequently the target DNA segments of interest were then amplified via PCR (polymerase chain reaction). Next the resultant pieces of DNA were sequenced. Numerous variants were identified through mutation analysis of the mitochondrial genome in this study. Synonymous mutation m.4769A>G was observed in 15 samples, indicating a consistent presence across subjects. The variant m.5046G>A was identified in two individuals and variant m.4916A>G was identified in one individual. All of these variants have been reported with disease. Our investigation additionally revealed three (3) unique (novel) genetic variants in CVD patients, which were identified as m.4733T>C, m.4947T>C, m.4502T>C. An in-depth examination of the entire mitochondrial genome of CVDs subjects will help to shed light on potential processes and treatment options and enhance our understanding of the complex link between genetic variants and cardiovascular diseases in Pakistan.

Keywords: sequence analysis of mtnd2 gene, families And segregating maternally inherited CVDS

INTRODUCTION

A broad spectrum of conditions that influence the heart and blood vessels are collectively referred to as Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) (Manolis, Manolis *et al.*, 2021). These diseases pose a significant threats to the global public health (Walden and Tomlinson 2012). Multiple studies have demonstrated that the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) contributes to the development and spread of cardiovascular disease and is associated with cell death (Fariha *et al.*, 2025). An increasing number of studies show that myocardial damage and progression of cardiac disease are caused by failure in mitochondrial dynamics, which is seen in several disease models, including blood pressure and metabolic disorders (Fuchs and Whelton 2020). It is crucial to identify biomarkers that indicate the risk of developing CVD in order to predict and treat this risk (Yu, Yan *et al.*, 2021). To successfully reduce the overall impact of CVD, it is crucial to take preventive measures (Vats 2023 ; Zouros 2020). Mitochondria have many functions beyond their primary role as energy producers (Shi, Zhang *et al.*, 2022). They can influence calcium responses and act as locations for Ca²⁺ storage (Boyman, Karbowski *et al.*, 2020). They have the ability to regulate cell development, differentiation, and apoptosis, among other functions (Gusdon, Votyakova *et al.*, 2008). Researchers often examine the mitochondrial

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proteome to detect and identify proteins that have been damaged or misfolded (Song, Herrmann *et al.*, 2021). The mtDNA consists of two strands - a heavy (H) strand, which is rich in guanine, and a light (L) strand (Vrablik, Dlouha *et al.*, 2021). The compact circular genome has 37 genes, with 12 genes dedicated to encoding structural components and 22 genes associated with tRNA and rRN (Polidori, Stocchi *et al.*, 2020). The NCR has two hypervariable regions (HVR) that exhibit many known variations, making it the most polymorphic locus in mtDNA (Lawless, Greaves *et al.*, 2020). To determine mitochondrial haplogroups and track the genetic lineage of human populations, it is necessary to sequence the HVRs of mtDNA (Poznyak, Ivanova *et al.* 2020, Habbane, Montoya *et al.*, 2021). Several mtDNA mutations have been linked to the cause of several chronic human illnesses, including CVD (Poznyak, Ivanova *et al.*, 2020, Batty, Bennett *et al.*, 2022). Mitochondria have been interrelated to the pathophysiology of CVDs, although the reasons for this remain unknown (Poznyak, Ivanova *et al.*, 2020). Maternally inherited disorders affecting the cardiovascular system, such as cardiomyopathy and stroke-like episodes, are brought on by rare, severe mtDNA single-nucleotide variants (mtSNVs) (Bicci 2022). Specific locations within the sequence of the mtND2 gene are frequently found to have mutations that are linked to CVDs (Alila, Rebai *et al.*, 2016). This particular genetic variant has been associated with a higher vulnerability to heart attack and high blood pressure in the Japanese population (Takagi, Yamada *et al.*, 2004). There are a number of variables that contribute to the development and progression of atherosclerosis, a hallmark of many CVDs, characterized by the deposition of plaque within artery walls, which ultimately leads to the narrowing and restriction of blood flow (Ciumărnean, Milaciu *et al.*, 2021). Efforts to eliminate smoking, improve diet and increase physical activity have had some effect in lowering CVD mortality rates (Organization 2011, Roth, Mensah *et al.*, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

DNA Extraction

The DNA extraction procedure commenced with the collection of 300µL of blood. Lysis buffer for breakdown, 2µl of β-mercaptoethanol (BME) to aid in protein denaturation and disrupt disulphide bonds, and 0.5µl of Proteinase K to aid in protein digestion with pH level of 8. 300µl of the lysis stock solution was added to the tube which contained the blood sample. After performing 10-15 inversions, add 300µL of PCI to each tube to perform purification of DNA and eliminate proteins that exist. A pipette was utilized to transfer the uppermost stratum, which contained DNA, to freshly prepared and clearly labeled tubes. In order to precipitate the DNA, 500µl of isopropanol at a low temperature is added to each tube, followed by vortexing for a duration of 3 secs. To dry the pellet at a temperature of 55°C, cautiously discard the ethanol (supernatant) and turn it upside down onto a new sheet of paper. In the final step, we added 50µl of ddH₂O (deionized water) to each tube, vortex it vigorously, and left it at room temperature for 10 mins.

DNA Confirmation

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In order to produce a 1% gel for the purpose of DNA confirmation, 49 millilitres of distilled water, one millilitre of 50X TAE buffer, and half a gramme of agar powder were mixed together. After boiling the solution, add 8 μ l of ethidium bromide, which has a concentration of 20mg/mL. Using a pipette, transfer 2 μ l of genomic DNA and 1 μ l of blue dye into every well of the sample.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

Specific regions of mtDNA were amplified with an aid of thermal cycler. The NCBI primer tool was used to generate a forward and reverse primers. The sequence contained the mtND2 gene, which has a length of around 1041 base pairs. The genomic bands later appears and become detectable under the transilluminator when exposed to ultraviolet light.

Sequencing of mtND2 gene

The DNA samples that had been amplified were prepared. In order to identify and assess any mutations that may have occurred in the mtND2 gene, the sequences were investigated by comparing them to the Revised Cambridge reference sequence.

RESULTS

Detection of extracted DNA

The isolated DNA was analysed using 1% agarose gel electrophoresis and visualised with a transilluminator.

Fig. 1- Gel Electrophoresis of Genomic DNA Extracted from Blood Samples Isolated from Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) Patients in District Mansehra. S1-S16 represent the selected samples for analysis.

MT-ND2 gene amplification

1042bp product was yield. For the confirmation of size, 1kb Ladder was loaded as a marker.

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Fig. 2- PCR analysis of ND2 Gene of the CVD patients (L=100bp, S1-S16 represent the

selected samples for analysis)

Prevalance of CVD vs Normal Patients

Fig. 3- Distribution of patients in a research study, comparing the number of patients with CVD against normal control.

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Prevalance of CVD in Male and Female Patients

Fig. 4- Distribution of male and female participants selected for the study on cardiovascular disease (CVD) across different age group.

Age wise Distribution

Fig. 5- Distribution of cardiovascular disease (CVD) cases across different age groups.

Family 1

Family1 has been marked CVD positive as mother, father and sister are affected by cardiovascular disease.

Sample S-1 (S1)

The patient is a 70 years old male with a CVD. The nucleotide alignment was determined using rCRS. In the mitochondrial encoded ND2 gene, a synonymous variant was found at position 4769A>G.

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Query 4460 TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC 4519
Sbjct 249 TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC 308
Query 4520 ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACAT 4579
Sbjct 309 ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACAT 368
Query 4580 GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCaaaaaaaaTAAACCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT 4639
Sbjct 369 GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAATAAACCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT 428
Query 4640 CAAGTATTTCTCACGAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGTATCCTCTTCAA 4699
Sbjct 429 CAAGTATTTCTCACGAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGTATCCTCTTCAA 488
Query 4700 CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAAT 4759
Sbjct 489 CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAAT 548
Query 4760 AATCATAATAGGATATAGCAATAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAGA 4819
Sbjct 549 AATCATAATGGATATAGCAATAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAGA 608
Query 4820 GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAACTAGC 4879
Sbjct 609 GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAACTAGC 668
Query 4880 CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT 4939
Sbjct 669 CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT 728
    
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Fig. 6- Alignment of ND2 gene of sample S-1, Family 1 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

Fig. 7- Alignment of ND2 gene of sample S-2, Family 1 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

Sample S-2 (S2)

The male 54-year-old patient suffered from obesity for the previous 42 years. The alignments of the nucleotides were evaluated against reference Cambridge sequence (rCRS). A synonymous mutation was found at position m.4769A>G.

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Query	4460	TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC	4519
Sbjct	249	TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC	308
Query	4520	ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAATAACAT	4579
Sbjct	309	ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAATAACAT	368
Query	4580	GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT	4639
Sbjct	369	GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT	428
Query	4640	CAAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA	4699
Sbjct	429	CAAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA	488
Query	4700	CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA	4759
Sbjct	489	CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA	548
Query	4760	AATCATAAATCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAGA	4819
Sbjct	549	AATCATAAATCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAGA	608
Query	4820	GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAGC	4879
Sbjct	609	GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAGC	668
Query	4880	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT	4939
Sbjct	669	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT	728

Fig. 8- Alignment of ND2 gene of sample S-2, Family 1 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

Fig. 9- Sequencing Chromatogram of identified m.4769A>G variant in patient S-2 of family 1

Sample S-3 (S3)

The female patient, 63 years old, has had hypertension for the previous 12 years. Alignment of nucleotides was performed by comparing them to the rCRS. One synonymous variant was found at location m.4769A>G. the variant is considered synonymous.

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Query 4460 TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC 4519
Sbjct 248 TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC 307
Query 4520 ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAATAAACAT 4579
Sbjct 308 ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAATAAACAT 367
Query 4580 GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCACAGAAGCTGCCAT 4639
Sbjct 368 GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCACAGAAGCTGCCAT 427
Query 4640 CAAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA 4699
Sbjct 428 CAAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA 487
Query 4700 CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA 4759
Sbjct 488 CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA 547
Query 4760 AATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAGA 4819
Sbjct 548 AATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAGA 607
Query 4820 GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAGC 4879
Sbjct 608 GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAGC 667
Query 4880 CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT 4939
Sbjct 668 CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT 727
    
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Fig. 10- Alignment of ND2 gene of sample S-3 of family 1 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

Fig. 11- Sequencing Chromatogram of identified m.4769A>G variant in patient S-3 of family

Sample S-4 (S4)

29-year-old female patient has been diagnosed with hypertension for the last 2 years. The patient's family history reported a history of cardiovascular diseases and hypertension. The alignments of the nucleotides were compared against rCRS, which revealed no variants in mtND2 gene.

Family 2

Three samples were collected from family 2, which consists of two generations of suffering. The family had been marked as CVD-positive. Using the most recent Cambridge Reference sequence (reference NC_012920.1), the sample was aligned.

Sample S-5 (S5)

A 56-year-old male patient from the first generation of family 2 was diagnosed with high blood pressure, high cholesterol and diabetes 41. Nucleotide alignments against rCRS were carried

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out, and the findings demonstrated variations at two distinct locations in the ND2 gene. The synonymous variants were identified at position m.4502T>C and m.4769A>G.

Fig. 12- Alignment of ND2 gene of sample S-5 of family 2 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

Fig. 13- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.4502T>C identified in Patient S-5 of family 2

Fig. 14- Sequencing Chromatogram of identified 4769A>G variant in patient S-5 of family 2

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Sample S-6 (S6)

Hypertension was diagnosed in a 41-year-old female at the age of 31. 4733T>C, 4769A>G and 4947T>C in mitochondrial encoded ND2 gene. The variations are synonymous which have no effect in proteins structure.

Query	4466	ACTA ATTAATCC CCTGGGCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGGCACACTCAT	4525
Sbjct	254	ACTAATTAATCCCCTGGGCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGGCACACTCAT	313
Query	4526	CACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACATGCTAGC	4585
Sbjct	314	CACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACATGCTAGC	373
Query	4586	TTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACcaaaaaaaTAAACCCTCGTTCACAGAAAGCTGCCATCAAGTA	4645
Sbjct	374	TTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCACAGAAAGCTGCCATCAAGTA	433
Query	4646	TTTCCTCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAACAATAT	4705
Sbjct	434	TTTCCTCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAACAATAT	493
Query	4706	ACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCA TAT TACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAAATAATCAT	4765
Sbjct	494	ACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCA TAT TACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAAATAATCAT	553
Query	4766	A T AGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTTCTGAGTCCCAGAGGTTAC	4825
Sbjct	554	A T AGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTTCTGAGTCCCAGAGGTTAC	613
Query	4826	CCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCATATGACAAAAACTAGCCCCAT	4885
Sbjct	614	CCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCATATGACAAAAACTAGCCCCAT	673
Query	4886	CTCAATCATATACCAAACTCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCTCTCAAT	4945
Sbjct	674	CTCAATCATATACCAAACTCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCTCTCAAT	733
Query	4946	T TATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCAAAATCTT	5005
Sbjct	734	T TATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCAAAATCTT	793
Query	5006	AGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGCAGTTCTACCGTACAACCCTAA	5065
Sbjct	794	AGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGCAGTTCTACCGTACAACCCTAA	853
Query	5066	CATAACCATTCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCCTAACTACTACCGCATTCTACTACT	5125
Sbjct	854	CATAACCATTCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCCTAACTACTACCGCATTCTACTACT	913
Query	5126	CAACTTAAACTCCAGCACCCAGACCCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAGCTAACATG	5185
Sbjct	914	CAACTTAAACTCCAGCACCCAGACCCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAGCTAACATG	973
Query	5186	ACTAACACCCTTAATTCATCCACCCCTCCTCTCCCTAGGAGGCCTGCCCCCGCTAACCGG	5245
Sbjct	974	ACTAACACCCTTAATTCATCCACCCCTCCTCTCCCTAGGAGGCCTGCCCCCGCTAACCGG	1033

Fig. 15- Alignment of ND2 gene of patient S-5 from Family 2 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1)

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Fig. 16- Sequencing Chromatogram of 4733T>C identified in Patient S6 of family 2

Fig. 17- Sequencing Chromatogram of 4769A>G identified in Patient S6 of family 2

Fig. 18- Sequencing Chromatogram of 4769A>G identified in Patient S6 of family 2

Fig. 19- Sequencing Chromatogram of and 4947T>C identified in Patient S6 of family 2

Sample S-7 (S7)

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A 23-year-old male control volunteer participated in the study. The nucleotide alignment was evaluated in comparison with the rCRS reference. Analysis demonstrates synonymous variation at three different position m.4733T>C, m.4769A>G and m.4947T>C.

Fig. 20- Alignment of ND2 gene, sample S-7 family 2 with rCRS (reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 21- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.4769A>G identified in Patient S6 of family 2

Query	4458	CTTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGC	4517
Sbjct	248	CTTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGC	307
Query	4518	ACACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAAATAAAC	4577
Sbjct	308	ACACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAAATAAAC	367
Query	4578	ATGCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAAATAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCC	4637
Sbjct	368	ATGCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAAATAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCC	427
Query	4638	ATCAAGTATTTCTCACGCAAGCAACCCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTC	4697
Sbjct	428	ATCAAGTATTTCTCACGCAAGCAACCCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTC	487
Query	4698	AACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATCTACCAATCAATATCATCATTAT	4757
Sbjct	488	AACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAACAATACCAATCAATATCATCATTAT	547
Query	4758	ATAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTTC TGAGTCCCA	4817
Sbjct	548	ATAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTTC TGAGTCCCA	607
Query	4818	GAGGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGCATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTA	4877
Sbjct	608	GAGGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGCATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTA	667
Query	4878	GCCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACATAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACT	4937
Sbjct	668	GCCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACATAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACT	727
Query	4938	CTCTCAATCTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTA AACCAACCCAGCTACGC	4997
Sbjct	728	CTCTCAATCTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTA AACCAACCCAGCTACGC	787
Query	4998	AAAACTTAGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGCAGTTCTACCGTAC	5057
Sbjct	788	AAAACTTAGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGCAGTTCTACCGTAC	847
Query	5058	AACCCTAACATAACCAATCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCCTAACTACTACCGCATT	5117
Sbjct	848	AACCCTAACATAACCAATCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCCTAACTACTACCGCATT	907
Query	5118	CTACTACTCAACTTAAACTCCAGCACACGACCCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAG	5177
Sbjct	908	CTACTACTCAACTTAAACTCCAGCACACGACCCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAG	967

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Fig. 22- Sequencing Chromatogram of and m.4947T>C identified in Patient S7 of family Family 3

The samples were matched with the most recent Cambridge Reference sequence (reference NC_012920.1), ensuring a reliable basis for comparing and analyzing genetic data.

Sample S-8 (S8)

A 62-year-old female experienced CVD at the age of 45, characterized by hypertension. Nucleotide alignments against the rCRS revealed changes at one location throughout the ND2 gene. The synonymous variant at position m.4769A>G was detected.

Query	4458	CTTCCCGTACTA ATTAATCC CCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGC	4517
Sbjct	247	CTTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGC	306
Query	4518	ACACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAAC	4577
Sbjct	307	ACACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAAC	366
Query	4578	ATGCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCaAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCC	4637
Sbjct	367	ATGCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCC	426
Query	4638	ATCAAGTATTTCTCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTC	4697
Sbjct	427	ATCAAGTATTTCTCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTC	486
Query	4698	AACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACATCATTA	4757
Sbjct	487	AACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACATCATTA	546
Query	4758	ATAATCATA TGC TATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCA	4817
Sbjct	547	ATAATCATA TGC TATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCA	606
Query	4818	GAGGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCATGACAAAAACTA	4877
Sbjct	607	GAGGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTCTCATGACAAAAACTA	666

Fig. 23- Alignment of the ND2 gene of patient S-8 from Family 3, with reference NC_012920.1

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Fig. 24- Sequencing Chromatogram of m4769A>G in patient S-8 from Family 3

Sample S-9 (S9)

At the age of 45, a 65-year-old male from Family 3 was diagnosed with hypertension. His medical history also revealed a variety of other conditions, including high blood pressure, high cholesterol, shortness of breath, dizziness, joint pain, chest pain and Stomach Pain The synonymous variant at position m.4769A>G was detected.

Query	4459	TTCCCGTACTA AATTAATCC CCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCCA	4518
Sbjct	250	TTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCCA	309
Query	4519	CACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCAC TGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCC TAGAAATAAACA	4578
Sbjct	310	CACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCAC TGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCC TAGAAATAAACA	369
Query	4579	TGCTAGCTTTTATTCAGTTCTAACCaaaaaaaaTAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCA	4638
Sbjct	370	TGCTAGCTTTTATTCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAA TAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCA	429
Query	4639	TCAAGTATTTCCCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCA	4698
Sbjct	430	TCAAGTATTTCCCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCA	489
Query	4699	ACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCATCAATACTCATCATTAA	4758
Sbjct	490	ACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCATCAATACTCATCATTAA	549
Query	4759	TAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAG	4818
Sbjct	550	TAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAG	609
Query	4819	AGGTTACCAAGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCC TGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAG	4878
Sbjct	610	AGGTTACCAAGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCC TGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAG	669
Query	4879	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTC	4938
Sbjct	670	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTC	729
Query	4939	TCTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCA	4998
Sbjct	730	TCTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCA	789

Fig. 25- Alignment of the ND2 gene of patient S-9 from Family 3, with reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 26- Sequencing Chromatogram of m4769A>G in patient S-9 from Family 3

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Sample S-10 (S10)

A 38-year-old control volunteer participated in the study, and his family has a history of cardiovascular disease. The nucleotide alignment was evaluated in comparison with the rCRS reference. The synonymous variant at position m.4769A>G was detected.

Fig. 27- Alignment of the ND2 gene of patient S-10 from Family 3, with reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 28- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.4769A>G in patient S-10 from Family 3

Family 4

The most recent Cambridge Reference Sequence rCRS (reference NC_012920.1) was used to align the samples, establishing a uniform framework for comparing and analyzing genetic data.

Sample S-11 (A11)

At the age of 41, the female member of Family 4 (aged 61) developed cardiovascular disease (CVD), with a specific diagnosis high blood pressure, obesity and diabetes. The nucleotides were aligned against the reference Cambridge sequence (rCRS). Two variations were founded at a specific location, including both synonymous and non-synonymous alterations. The non-synonymous mutations included a number of shifts, such as the G>A mutation at position m.5046G>A/p.Val191Ile, resulting in the replacement of isoleucine with valine. In contrast, synonymous variants at positions 4769A>G were identified.

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Query	4461	CCCCTACTAATTAAATCCCTGGGCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCACA	4520
Sbjct	246	CCCCTACTAATTAAATCCCTGGGCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCACA	305
Query	4521	CTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAAATAAACATG	4580
Sbjct	306	CTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAAATAAACATG	365
Query	4581	CTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAAATAAACCTCGTTCACAGAAAGCTGCCATC	4640
Sbjct	366	CTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAAATAAACCTCGTTCACAGAAAGCTGCCATC	425
Query	4641	AAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCTTCTAATAGCTACTCTCTCAAC	4700
Sbjct	426	AAGTATTTCTCAGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCTTCTAATAGCTACTCTCTCAAC	485
Query	4701	AATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATATCATCATTAAATA	4760
Sbjct	486	AATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATATCATCATTAAATA	545
Query	4761	ATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCAGTCTGAGTCCCAGAG	4820
Sbjct	546	ATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCAGTCTGAGTCCCAGAG	605
Query	4821	GTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGCACATCCGGCTGCTTCTTCTCATATGACAAAAACTAGCC	4880
Sbjct	606	GTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGCACATCCGGCTGCTTCTTCTCATATGACAAAAACTAGCC	665
Query	4881	CCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAACTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCTC	4940
Sbjct	666	CCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAACTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCTC	725
Query	4941	TCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAACCAAAACCAGCTACGCAAA	5000
Sbjct	726	TCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAACCAAAACCAGCTACGCAAA	785
Query	5001	ATCTTAGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGTCTACCCGTACAAC	5060
Sbjct	786	ATCTTAGCATACTCCTCAATTACCCACATAGGATGAATAATAGTCTACCCGTACAAC	845
Query	5061	CCTAACATAAACCAATTTCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCTTAACACTACCAGCATTCCTA	5120
Sbjct	846	CCTAACATAAACCAATTTCTTAATTTAACTATTTATATTATCTTAACACTACCAGCATTCCTA	905
Query	5121	CTACTCAACTTAAACTCCAGCACCAGACCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAGCTA	5180
Sbjct	906	CTACTCAACTTAAACTCCAGCACCAGACCCTACTACTATCTCGCACCTGAAACAAGCTA	965
Query	5181	ACATGACTAACACCCCTTAATTCATCCACCCTCCTCTCCCTAGGAGGCCTGCCCCCGCTA	5240
Sbjct	966	ACATGACTAACACCCCTTAATTCATCCACCCTCCTCTCCCTAGGAGGCCTGCCCCCGCTA	1025

Fig. 29- Alignment of the ND2 of patient S-11 (S11) from Family 4 with reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 30- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.4769A>G in patient S-11 (S11) of family 4

Fig. 31- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.5046G>A in patient S-11 (S11) of family 4
Sample S-12 (S12)

This case involves a 80-year-old male patient with a history of high blood pressure and heart valve block. Two variations were founded at a specific location, including both synonymous and non-synonymous alterations. The non-synonymous mutations included a number of shifts,

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such as the G>A mutation at position m.5046G>A/p.Val191Ile, resulting in the replacement of isoleucine with valine. In contrast, synonymous variants at positions 4769A>G were identified.

Fig. 32- Alignment of the ND2 of patient S-12 (S12) from Family 4 with reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 33- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.4769A>G in patient S-12 (S12) of family 4

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Fig. 34- Sequencing Chromatogram of m.5046G>A in patient S-12 (S12) of family 4 Sample S-13 (S13)

This case involves a 23-year-old male who was diagnosed with heart hole 19mm. The nucleotide alignments and rCRS were compared. The analysis identified two synonymous variants at position m.4769A>G and m.4916A>G in the MT-ND2 gene.

Query	4460	TCCCGTACTA ATTAATCC CCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC	4519
Sbjct	250	TCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCAC	309
Query	4520	ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACAT	4579
Sbjct	310	ACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCACTGATTTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCTAGAAATAAACAT	369
Query	4580	GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCaaaaaaTAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT	4639
Sbjct	370	GCTAGCTTTTATTCCAGTTCTAACCAAAAAAAAATAAACCCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCAT	429
Query	4640	CAAGTATTTCCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA	4699
Sbjct	430	CAAGTATTTCCACGCAAGCAACCGCATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCAA	489
Query	4700	CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA	4759
Sbjct	490	CAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATCATTAA	549
Query	4760	AATCATAA TAC CTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAGA	4819
Sbjct	550	AATCATAA TGC CTATAGCAATAAAACTAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACCTCTGAGTCCCAGA	609
Query	4820	GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTTCACATGACAAAACTAGC	4879
Sbjct	610	GGTTACCCAAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCTGCTTCTTTCACATGACAAAACTAGC	669
Query	4880	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCAC AA ACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT	4939
Sbjct	670	CCCCATCTCAATCATATACCAAATCTCTCCCTCAC AA ACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTCT	729
Query	4940	CTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCAA	4999
Sbjct	730	CTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCAA	789

Fig. 35- Sequencing Chromatogram of patient S-13 of family 4 with reference NC_012920.1

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Fig. 36- Sequencing Chromatogram of m. 4916A>G in patient S-13 (S13) of family 4

Fig. 37- Sequencing Chromatogram of m. 4969A>G in patient S-13 (S13) of family 4

Family 5

We used a rCRS (reference NC_012920.1), which allowed us to further investigate the potential genetic variables that might be linked to CVD in this family.

Sample S-14 (S14)

The patient is a 35-year-old woman who has suffered from cardiovascular disease (Heart attack, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, obesity) since she was 33. The nucleotide alignments were compared against rCRS, and no variations were detected in mtND2 gene.

Sample S-15 (S15)

The patient is a 65-year-old female who has suffered from cardiovascular disease (angiography, High B.P, Diabetics and obesity) since she was 53. No variants were identified in mtND2 gene

Sample S-16 (S16)

A 29-year-old control volunteer participated in the study, and his family has a history of angiography, High B.P and high cholesterol. The nucleotide alignment was evaluated in comparison with the rCRS reference. The synonymous variant at position m.4769A>G was detected.

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Query 4459 TTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCA 4518
Sbjct 250 TTCCCGTACTAATTAATCCCTGGCCCAACCCGTCATCTACTCTACCATCTTTGCAGGCA 309
Query 4519 CACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCAGTGAATTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAAATAACA 4578
Sbjct 310 CACTCATCACAGCGCTAAGCTCGCAGTGAATTTTTACCTGAGTAGGCCCTAGAAAATAACA 369
Query 4579 TGCTAGCTTTTATTCAGTTC TAACCaaaaaaaTAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCA 4638
Sbjct 370 TGCTAGCTTTTATTCAGTTC TAACCAAAAAAAAA TAAACCCTCGTTCCACAGAAGCTGCCA 429
Query 4639 TC AAGTATTTCTCCTCAGCAAGCAACCCGATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCA 4698
Sbjct 430 TC AAGTATTTCTCCTCAGCAAGCAACCCGATCCATAATCCTTCTAATAGCTATCCTCTTCA 489
Query 4699 ACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATATTA 4758
Sbjct 490 ACAATATACTCTCCGGACAATGAACCATAACCAATACTACCAATCAATACTCATATTA 549
Query 4759 TAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAAAC TAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAG 4818
Sbjct 550 TAATCATAATAGCTATAGCAATAAAAAC TAGGAATAGCCCCCTTTCACTTCTGAGTCCCAG 609
Query 4819 AGGTTACCCAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAG 4878
Sbjct 610 AGGTTACCCAGGCACCCCTCTGACATCCGGCCCTGCTTCTTCTCACATGACAAAAACTAG 669
Query 4879 CCCCCATCTCAATCATATACC AAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTC 4938
Sbjct 670 CCCCCATCTCAATCATATACC AAATCTCTCCCTCACTAAACGTAAGCCTTCTCCTCACTC 729
Query 4939 TCTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCA 4998
Sbjct 730 TCTCAATCTTATCCATCATAGCAGGCAGTTGAGGTGGATTAAACCAAACCCAGCTACGCA 789
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Fig. 38- Sequencing Chromatogram of patient S-16 of family 5 with reference NC_012920.1

Fig. 39- Sequencing Chromatogram of m4769A>G in patient S-16 from Family 5

Pathogenicity prediction of the identified variations

To analyze the pathogenicity of detected variations five different bioinformatics tools were used including, MitImpact 3D, SIFT (Sorting Intolerant from Tolerant), Polyphen2, PROVEAN (Protein Variation Effect Analyzer) and MutationTaster. These multi-tool techniques enabled an in-depth investigation of the variants, using MitImpact 3D's structural insights, SIFT and Polyphen2's functional predictions PROVEAN's variant effect analysis.

Pathogenicity Prediction using Pholyphen2 and SIFT

The SIFT pathogenicity scores illustrating the algorithm's ability to assess the tolerance of amino acid changes in protein sequences. And the PolyPhen-2 depicts pathogenicity scores emphasizing the tool's capacity to predict the impact of amino acid changes on protein structure and function. Such in-depth investigations help to grasp the implications of these differences in the context of the examined biological system.

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Fig. 40- Represent the PolyPhen-2 prediction for the genetic variation m.5046G>A/Val193Ile. A score greater than 0.5 denotes a potentially harmful effect, whilst a score of less than 0.5 denotes a benign influence on the structure and function of proteins.

pos	A	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	K	L	M	N	P	Q	R	S	T	V	W	Y
176R	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
177K	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
178I	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
179L	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
180A	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
181Y	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
182S	1.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
183S	1.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
184I	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
185T	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
186H	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
187M	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00
188G	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
189W	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
190M	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.01	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
191M	1.00	0.69	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.98	0.05	0.40	0.30	0.03	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.10	1.00	0.96	0.01
192A	1.00	1.00	0.05	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.61	0.04	0.32	0.14	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.18	0.32	0.71	0.01
193V	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.31	0.00
194L	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.00	1.00	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.00

Fig. 41- Depicts the SIFT-predicted genetic variant m. m.5046G>A/Val193Ile. Specifically, a score less than 0.5 suggests a potentially pathogenic effect, while a score greater than 0.5 indicates a neutral impact on the structure and function of protein.

DISCUSSION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) encompass a broad spectrum of conditions that affect the heart and blood vessels, constituting a significant global health challenge (Walden and Tomlinson 2012). One such mutation is the MT-ND2 m. 5178C>A variant. This mutation has been associated with a reduced risk of several diseases, including myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular disease, type 2 diabetes and atherosclerosis (Ohkubo, Nakagawa *et al.* 2002; Takagi, Yamada *et al.*, 2004; Liao, Pang *et al.*, 2008; Ito). The MT-ND2 m. 5178C>A mutation's protective role against myocardial infarction and cerebrovascular disease may be linked to its influence on mitochondrial efficiency and oxidative stress regulation (Stewart and Chinnery 2021). In our study, we analyzed mitochondrial encoded ND2 gene from 16 individuals diagnosed with CVD, to explore genetic variations related to CVD. Our genetic analysis found a substantial amount of fifteen (29) variations in mtND2 gene, Specifically, A>G variant at position m.4769, T>C variant at position m.4733, G>A variant at location m.5046, and C>T variant at position m.5337. Similarly, m.5339C>T, m.4502T>C, m.4947T>C, m.4916A>G, m.4719T>G, m.4932C>A, m.4947T>C and m.4936C>G variations were

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identified. The m.4769A>G mutation, previously linked to Leigh Syndrome, and male infertility, has been identified in 15 individuals, affecting mitochondrial complex I assembly and contributing to the disease's pathogenesis as documented by Ugalde *et al.* (2007) and Barbhuiya *et al.*, 2016. This mutation is well-documented to be associated with fertilization failure by Chinese study carried out by Zhang *et al.*, 2018. Additionally, our research found many unique genetic variations at positions m.4733T>C, m.4502T>C, and m.4947T>C in CVD patients. The scientific literature has not shown any proof of these genetic changes.

CONCLUSION

Our study found no variations in the MtND2 gene directly associated with cardiovascular disease (CVD). Our research has reported some reference to CVD-related mtDNA encoded ND2 gene variations that are novel in the literature. To find out more about the genetics of cardiovascular disease, future study should include an in-depth investigation of the complete mitochondrial genome. Additionally, efforts should be made to promote awareness about the significance of genetic testing and to give affected families with adequate counselling.

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